

A successful private company in industrial developing country. Managers' perspective

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Abstract

A project was conducted during October 2013 at Afranet, a private IT company in Iran to highlight the reasons for its success in a highly uncertain external environment with high degree of changes. The project has been conducted using the “Holistic System Approach” theory, in which the individual system components as well as their interaction and the synergic effects of the whole were studied. Data on system components, i.e., technology, human resource, management, information, the external and internal environment were collected using interview and questionnaire methods. Regarding the system output, an on-line questionnaire survey were conducted among over 1000 companies receiving different types of IT support from the Afranet company. Two questionnaires were conducted among top and middle managers as well as supervisors of the company. The managers perspective regarding e.g. participation, problem solving, promotion, satisfaction, work load, responsibilities, authorities, motivation, quality of working life, happiness at work and information flow is presented in this paper.